

Efficient Navigation for Parcel Delivery

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Abstract. The rapid growth of delivery services has driven the demand for innovative strategies to improve logistics efficiency. The team delivery approach presents new opportunities for optimization. This study proposes a method for deriving efficient delivery navigation to reduce task completion times. A novel evaluation index is formulated, and a simulation is conducted to compare the proposed method with existing operations. We will demonstrate that the optimized delivery paths derived from the method significantly streamline delivery tasks. Future work will refine the simulation to incorporate diverse parcel types and additional parameters, further enhancing its practical applicability in dynamic delivery environments.

Keywords. Parcel Delivery, Traveling Salesman Problem, Optimization

1. Introduction

As the use of delivery services continues to grow, ways to improve the efficiency of delivery service industries are being avidly sought. There is a substantial body of research on freight logistics and parcel delivery. Sachan and Datta (2005) conducted a systematic review of logistics and supply chain management (SCM) studies, focusing on the methodologies employed in each. Lee and Ueng (1999) developed an integer programming model for vehicle routing problems to ensure fairness by balancing workloads among delivery persons. Regarding the optimal allocation of routes and delivery persons, Dantzig and Ramser (1956) applied linear programming to determine the assignment of gasoline delivery trucks to destination gas stations, minimizing the total mileage traveled by all trucks.

Two practices are common now, single delivery (Fig. 1(a)(b)), and team delivery (Fig. 1(a)(c)), which was introduced recently. This study proposes a method for deriving efficient delivery navigation in order to shorten the delivery task completion time for team delivery. To examine whether this

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method provides a more efficient service, parameters derived from the findings of a survey were employed in a delivery simulation.

Figure 1. Normal- and team-delivery system.

2. Method for Deriving Delivery Paths in Team Delivery Operation

In team delivery, the team consists of a sales driver (*SD*) and field cast (*FC*) working in cooperation as they make the rounds to destinations. The *SD* hands parcels over to the *FC* at transfer locations *P*, the *SD* and *FC* then make their own deliveries, meet at the next *P*, and continue this sequence until they have completed all of their deliveries (Fig. 1(c)). In this study, the delivery problem in team delivery is formulated mathematically. As the efficiency evaluation index, the delivery task completion time *T* is set by summing the travel time over the delivery path, the time spent at each delivery destination, and the time spent at the transfer location *P*. We have investigated a method for deriving an efficient delivery path to minimize index *T*.

Delivery problems in team delivery resemble problems in which multiple people pass through multiple points and can be considered a variation of the multiple traveling salesman problem (m-TSP), with the difference that the delivery persons meet at some locations of P . Previously employed procedures for handling the traveling salesman problem such as the fuzzy c -means algorithm (Watanabe et al., 2001), the tour-splitting heuristic (Fredrickson et al., 1978), the perspective ratio (Miyata and Hamamatsu, 1998), and sweep (Gillet and Miller, 1974) were combined with a genetic algorithm (GA) to construct a new method for the optimal delivery navigation (Fig. 2.)

Method (4) is a new method we propose in this study that extends method (3). It uses a genetic algorithm (GA) for the purpose of determining the number and the locations of P s but retains some flexibility in deriving the optimal P (upper section of Figure 2). Specifically, it considers multiple destinations between two zones and nearby offices/homes as candidate locations for P s, and subsequently computes combinations of P s (gene) by selecting a single P from the candidates' pool. This is followed by repeating a certain number of crossovers. The solution is obtained by deriving the shortest T gene.

Method (7) is a novel approach proposed in this study to identify a small value for the evaluation index T using GA, as shown in the bottom section of Figure 2. The process consists of the following steps: Creating an array that arranges all destinations in order of their angular position relative to the center of gravity. Establishing arrays of handover points, which are randomly selected from the destinations. Extracting the handover points from each array (gene). This process is followed by a series of crossover operations, where recombination occurs at a randomly determined position between genes with low evaluation index T . The final solution is obtained by identifying the gene with the shortest T .

In this study, we recognize that the limit on the number of parcels that can be loaded onto a truck is a factor to be considered at delivery bases where parcels are assigned to trucks. We treat therefore the number of parcels loaded onto a truck as a fixed condition and focus instead on the limit on the number of parcels delivery persons can carry at one time.

Figure 2. Differences in delivery route derivation methods.

3. Evaluation of Delivery Path Deviation Method

A survey of the actual delivery operations was conducted in a low-rise residential area of approximately $600 \text{ m} \times 750 \text{ m}$ near Okusawa Station in Setagaya-ku, Tokyo. Data were collected from actual delivery operations carried out by team-based delivery and collection units of Yamato Transport Co., Ltd. (Tokyo, Japan), a leading door-to-door parcel delivery service provider with a 41% market share in Japan. During the survey, an investigator accompanied each delivery person during the morning hours, when delivery volumes were highest, recording the time, location, speed, and other relevant attributes for each delivery instance using a GPS tracker and a custom-built recording app designed specifically for the study. Parameters for delivery simulation, such as the number of parcels m , the number n of transfer locations P , and the times necessary for each task, were set.

Seven optimization methods (Fig. 2) were employed with five combinations of m and n for 50 cases with differing delivery destinations to determine the delivery paths. The histograms show that, in terms of computation time, Method (5) outperforms other methods in deriving the evaluation index T when the number of destinations, including P s, is small. However, when m is sufficiently large, the increasing complexity of the problem renders Method (5) infeasible within a reasonable computation time. The results for the continuous two-dimensional space 500 m square showed that method (4) was the superior method when there was a large number m of parcels. Comparing these results to those of the exact solution for the evaluation index T and the calculation time, the error for T in method (4) was kept to about 2% and the calculation time was dramatically reduced (Fig. 3.) According to Method (7), the evaluation value was kept to about 0.8%, however, it took much calculation time for the case $m=200, n=20$.

Figure 3. Comparison of delivery route optimization methods.

4. Analysis by Delivery Simulation

Fig. 4(a) shows a result of a simulation reproducing actual deliveries that was performed using the parameters taken from the surveys. Fig. 4(b) shows a simulation result of deliveries optimized by method (4). We can see that optimized deliveries provide shortened distances for both *SD* and *FC*, and that the evaluation index T was also excellent (Fig. 4(c).) Thus, as long as information about the delivery destinations and the number of parcels is available, it may be possible to streamline the delivery tasks by optimizing both the transfer locations and the travel path.

Figure 4. Actual and optimal delivery routes.

The relationship between the evaluation index T and the number n of transfer locations P , where the SD and FC meet, was examined via a simulation. In this simulation, n was reduced from 12 to 6 locations and the lists of parcels to be transferred, and the delivery paths were optimized. In other words, when n is large, the driver and delivery staff must meet frequently, leading to inefficiencies. This further decreased the delivery task comple-

tion time. This method can be expected to improve safety during travel for deliveries (Fig. 5(a).) As shown in Fig. 5(c), T is minimized by values of n satisfying the approximation equation in Fig. 5(b) when the maximum parcel capacity q is low (both SD and FC deliver q parcels). Large variations in T disappear at higher values of q . Thus, optimizing q and n reduces the burden on delivery persons and will enable more efficient team delivery.

However, we believe that a field experiment should be conducted to assess whether the optimal solution calculated through the simulation is practically feasible.

Figure 5. Model parameters and evaluation indices.

5. Summary and Conclusions

A formulation was developed for an evaluation index for delivery navigations in team delivery, and a method for deriving an efficient delivery path was proposed by comparing it with the existing operation and the exact solution. A delivery simulation based on the proposed method was performed and the optimized delivery path was compared with the actual delivery path. The results showed that the method is capable of streamlining delivery tasks. In the future, further surveys will be carried out and the simulation will be improved to account for different parcel types and other parameters. For instance, there is a demand for both the delivery and collection of parcels. The current model does not address how to handle collection requests made in real time. To overcome this limitation, it is necessary

to enhance the optimization model by developing a dynamic optimization approach that can update the optimal solution in real time in response to such requests.

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